

Academic Performance of Criminology Graduates and its Impact on the Licensure Examination for Criminologists

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Abstract:- Passing the licensure examination which is administered by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) one of the biggest accomplishments of all board program graduates here in the Philippines. This study aimed to analyze the Academic Performance of Criminology Graduates and its Impact on the Licensure Examination for Criminologists. Descriptive type of quantitative research method, documentary analysis employed to determine the academic performance of criminology graduates and the Licensure Examination for Criminologists. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the academic performance and licensure examination. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was utilized to test the relationship between the graduate's academic performance and licensure examination performance. The academic performance of the examinees who passed the licensure examination has a very satisfactory verbal interpretation based on the scheduled examination. all their weighted average mean were 85 and above. While those who unsuccessfully passed the exam have only 81 – 84.25 grade bracket which means they were consonantly in satisfactory verbal interpretation. The performance in the licensure examination for Criminologists of the examinees of SIT (passers and Non – Passers) showed that they have consonants; they have both high weighted averages mean in the subject areas of Law Enforcement Administration and Lowest average mean in the subject area of Correctional Administration. There is a negative weak correlation between the academic performance concerning licensure examination, the academic performance of the graduates who passed the licensure examination, and those who failed the examination, their correlation was moderately positively correlated with each other. Hence, Further study on evaluating the instructional design and assessment of the strategies of faculty handling major subjects in criminology program basis on cascading the intervention program for improvement of the student's performance in 6 major subject areas in criminology board examination.

Keywords:- Academic Performance, Criminology Graduates, Impact, Licensure Examination.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quality basic education is one of the most important educational institutions that influences and is influenced by other educational institutions Mensah, et. al (2020), The institution endlessly offers quality education, innovating instruction practice and enhancing graduates' performances serve up as an input for professional development Quiambao. et al. (2015), Similarly, graduates' licensing performance can reflect the quality and effectiveness of their respective institutions' instruction. The top priority of any Higher Education Institution (HEI) and State University and College (SUC) here in the Philippines is high performance in the board program licensing examinations conducted by the PRC. Gabasa&Raqueño (2021), This examination is designed to measure the students' knowledge, competency, skills, and attitude in the practice of their respective profession as stated by Mohammed and Mohammed (2017), The success of an institution can be measured through the performance of its graduate in the licensure examination. As stated by Manalo and Obligar (2013), the decrease in the passing rate of Filipino graduates in the various licensure examinations is a symptom of the deteriorating quality of higher education institutions in the Philippines which can be characterized by the variety and level of competency of the faculty Bautista, Ducanes and David (2019), hence, home and family factor have a high influence on the success in CLE, while student factor, school factor, review center factor, and personal factor have average influence. Albina et al (2021), truancy affects academic performance drastically and sometimes even leads to school dropout. other factors such as students' parental levels of education and income, textbooks availability and accessibility, libraries, practical laboratories, meals provision, and teachers have tremendous effects on the academic performance of students at school Brew, Nketiah, and Koranteng (2021)

Hence, an outcome-based curriculum must be adopted to periodically monitor the academic performance and behavior as well as the result of the study habits of the students Laguador and Dizon (2013), The result of this study is consistent with that of Howell, Kurns, and Antil (2013) explicating that the curriculum being offered in higher education programs is intended to prepare students to achieve minimum competencies related to a specific vocation or profession.

The Faculty members should regularly update their knowledge and competencies along with the subject areas being handled to contribute to the increased passing rate, enforce a stringent screening and retention policies for criminology students as regards grade point average and curriculum enrichment, and periodic review the course contents, in consultation with the subject-experts, should be done Guadamor (2020), all criminology chairpersons and faculty members must do a careful and thorough examination of the subjects included in the professional components of the BS Criminology curriculum Asuncion (2020), State universities and colleges and other private institutions should adopt several methods to achieve a high passing percentage. Casama and Ventayen (2020)

A graduate with a Baccalaureate degree in Criminology is required to pass the Licensure Examination from the Professional Regulation Commission of the Philippines to be considered a Licensed Criminologist to be given full authority to practice the profession. This is mandated under Republic Act No. 11131 which states that “the law creating the Board of Criminology. To achieve this expectation, the quality of teaching and learning in higher education institutions must meet the profession's standards. The passing percentage in the board examination should be higher than the national passing percentage as a measure of the output of higher education institutions' quality of teaching and learning.

As one of the province's Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering the Bachelor of Science in Criminology, Solis Institute of Technology aspires to produce quality graduates and professionals who are competent and mature enough to face the real world of work after graduation and board examination. Thus, the researchers envision helping the academic institution to increase its board examination percentage through active engagement of internal and external stakeholders, implementation of well-planned programs, relevant curriculum alignment, admission and

retention policies and enhancement courses, mock board examination, using the output of this study as a ready reference.

➤ *Objective of the Study*

The study aimed to analyze the Academic Performance of Criminology Graduates and Its Impact on The Licensure Examination for Criminologists (LEC) Of Solis Institute of Technology (SIT) From 2017 to 2021. Specifically, this study was guided by the following objectives: What is the academic performance of criminology graduates based on their scholastic records? What is the performance of criminology graduates in the licensure examination for criminologists from 2017 – 2021? Is there a correlation between the academic performance of criminology graduates and the Licensure Examination for Criminologists?

II. ANALYTICAL CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on the **theory of attribution** developed by Shrestha (2017) and Weiner (1992). Learners learn affected by both personal factors, previously learned knowledge and past experiences, and environmental factors like the environment of the home or school. Both these factors are the variables that affected the types of attributions most likely to be made by the individuals.

This study concentrates on the Academic Performance of Criminology Graduates and Its Impact on The Licensure Examination for Criminologist (LEC) Of Solis Institute of Technology (SIT) From 2017 to 2021 the researcher examines the yearly performance of the Criminology graduates in their academic and licensure examination. The increase, as well as the decrease in percentages, shall be carefully observed and analyzed in order to arrive at a higher level of accuracy in the understanding of the impact of the academic performance in their licensure examination.

Fig 1: Conceptual Paradigm

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The researcher utilized the descriptive type of quantitative research method, documentary analysis was employed to determine the academic performance of criminology graduates and the Licensure Examination for Criminologist examinees performance from 2017 – 2021 were the subjects of this study. the study analyzed the relationship and strength of correlation between the graduates’ academic performance and Licensure examination for Criminologist performance.

➤ *Population and locale of the Study*

This study will be conducted at Solis Institute of Technology (SIT) one of the private higher education institutions in the province of Sorsogon Specifically situated in the Municipality of Bulan. Founded by the late Congressman Jose G. Solis, it offers Secondary to Tertiary levels. A premier school in the province offering BS Criminology Program since 2000. The participants of the study were the BS Criminology Graduates of this institution who had undergone the Licensure Examination for Criminologists (LEC) from the year 2017 to 2021. Both the first timer and repeater examinees were included, there have two examination schedules conducted every year by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). There were 105 passers and 267 non-passers with an overall 372 total respondents.

Fig 2: Solis Institute of Technology (SIT)

➤ *Data Gathering Tools*

The researchers, to gather their primary data, made a request letter addressed to the office of the head registrar to furnish them with records of the academic performance of criminology graduates and from the record office of the Professional Regulation Commission for the list of takers from the years cover of the research. From the furnished record, the researchers analyzed, tallied, and tabulated the data to arrive at their objectives which are to describe and compare the academic and licensure performance in the six professional board subjects which are Law Enforcement

Administration, Criminal Jurisprudence, and Procedure, correctional Administration, Criminalistics, Criminal Sociology, CDI. The researcher sought the assistance of their statistician in computing the mean rank and presenting it on the table.

➤ *Data Gathering Procedures*

The approval of the School Vice President on the conduct of the study was sought. When the approval of the School Vice president was secured, request letters were forwarded to the office of the Dean of College of Criminology and the registrar’s office of the Solis Institute of Technology (SIT) to obtain the academic profile in General Education Subjects and Major Subjects. The result of the Licensure Examination for Criminologists was obtained from the office of the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). No monetary value was involved in this study.

➤ *Treatment of Data*

Mean and standard deviation was used to describe the academic performance and licensure examination for criminologist performance of criminology graduates of SIT. These were categorized along with the following descriptive value.

Grades	Percentage Equivalent (PE)	PE Average	Verbal Interpretation
1.00	98 - 100	99	Excellent
1.2	95 - 97	96	Superior
1.5	92 - 94	93	Superior
1.7	89 - 91	90	Very satisfactory
2.0	86 - 88	87	Very satisfactory
2.2	83 - 85	84	Satisfactory
2.5	80 - 82	81	Satisfactory
2.7	77- 79	78	Fairly satisfactory
3.0	75 - 76	75.5	Barely satisfactory
5.0	60 - 74	67	Unsatisfactory

Table 1:grading system in Solis Institute of Technology

Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was utilized to test the relationship between the graduate’s academic performance and licensure examination for criminologist performance. It was introduced by Karl Pearson in 1901. The size of the correlation varies from +1 through 0 to -1.

➤ *Ethical Consideration*

An ethical consideration review and approval were also sought from the school vice president and the Solisian Board of Pioneer (SBP). Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the data gathering stage. The students’ identities were withheld by utilizing their Names and student numbers as their identifiers. The data are used exclusively for this study alone.

IV. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Academic Performance of the Examinees Based on the Scholastic Records (Passers and Non-Passers)

Table 1 presents the academic Performance of the Examinees who were passed the Licensure Examination for Criminologists based on the scholastic records of passers. The table shows the examination schedule, the result in General Education and Major Subjects, the Weighted mean as well as

the Verbal Interpretation. December 2018 has the highest weighted average mean of 90.25 which is verbally interpreted as very satisfactory, having a 91.5 average mean for general education subjects and 89 mean average for major subjects. While the lowest weighted average mean of 85 was shown in December 2017 licensure examination with satisfactory interpretation. data shows also that females perform well academically compared to male examinees showing a high average percentage mean in both general and major subjects.

Table 1: Academic performance of the Examinees Based on the Scholastic Records (Passers)

Date of Examination	GENERAL EDUCATION SUBJECTS			MAJOR SUBJECTS			Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL		
JUNE 2017	86	88	87	86	91	88.5	87.75	Very Satisfactory
DECEMBER 2017	86	82	84	86	86	86	85	Satisfactory
JUNE 2018	86	84	85	88	89	88.5	86.75	Very Satisfactory
DECEMBER 2018	89	94	91.5	88	90	89	90.25	Very Satisfactory
JUNE 2019	86	92	89	87	90	89	89	Very Satisfactory
DECEMBER 2019	85	89	87	87	89	88	87.5	Very Satisfactory
JUNE 2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
DECEMBER 2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
JUNE 2021	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
DECEMBER 2021	83	87	85	90	88	89	87	Very Satisfactory
Weighted Mean	85.83	88	86.92	87.42	89	88.28	87.60	Very Satisfactory

Source: Solis Registrar Office, Bulan, Sorsogon

It is reflected in the table that those examinees who take the examination academically perform well while they are studying. This is supported by Rabanal (2016) analyzed the performance of the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) 2013 graduates of the University of Northern Philippines (UNP) and determined the relationship between academic achievement to LET performance was also looked into. The findings revealed that academic achievement is significantly related to LET performance. Educational Institutions should continue to seek professional development ventures for the improvement of teaching competence and professional preparations. Thus, come out with quality output

in the success of board examination leading graduates towards employment.

Table 2 show the distribution of the respondent in this study specifically the academic performance of non-passers in General Education and Major Subjects. The majority of the data verbally interpreted as Satisfactory, June 2019 with 84.25 was the highest weighted average mean, followed by the weighted mean enumerated descending in order, 83 December 2021, June 2017, December 2017, December 2018, where having 82 weighted mean average, were in June 2018 and June 2019 were only 81 weighted means.

Table 2: Academic performance of the Examinees Based on the Scholastic Records (Non-Passers)

Date of Examination	GENERAL EDUCATION SUBJECTS			MAJOR SUBJECTS			Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL		
JUNE 2017	81	82	81.5	83	84	83.5	82.5	Satisfactory
DECEMBER 2017	84	82	83	81	82	81.5	82.25	Satisfactory
JUNE 2018	80	81	80.5	80	83	81.5	81	Satisfactory
DECEMBER 2018	82	83	82.5	85	81	82	82.25	Satisfactory
JUNE 2019	80	83	81.5	83	81	82	81.75	Satisfactory
DECEMBER 2019	85	81	83	86	85	85.5	84.25	Satisfactory
JUNE 2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
DECEMBER 2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
JUNE 2021	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
DECEMBER 2021	84	0	84	82	0	82	83	Satisfactory
Weighted Mean	82.28	82	82.28	82.85	82.66	82.57	82.42	Satisfactory

Source: Solis Registrar Office, Bulan, Sorsogon

In comparison to the Weighted mean of the passers from the non-passers in their academic performance, the weighted average mean of the passers is higher than the non-passers. Cortez M.T. et. al. (2017) stated that there is a need to strengthen and improve the professional dimensions of the examinees by knowing the important factors in measuring the quality of education and its whole system in general

B. General Weighted Mean of the Examinees per Subject Area in the Licensure Examinations for Criminologist Every Examination from 2017-2021 (Passers and Non-Passers)

Table 3 shows the General weighted mean of the examinees per subject area in the Licensure Examination for Criminologists from 2017 -2021. Presented in descending order, the following are gathered per subject area: rank 1, law Enforcement Administration with a weighted mean of 80.10, rank 2, Crime Detection and Investigation, 80.05, Rank 3, the weighted average mean with 78.23, rank 4, Criminalistics 77.44, rank 5, Criminal Law and Jurisprudence 77.26, rank 6, Criminal Sociology, Ethics and Human Relation with the average of 77.83 and rank 7, Correctional Administration with a total weighted mean of 76.73.

Table 3: General Weighted Mean of the Examinees per Subject Area in the Licensure Examinations for Criminologists Every Examination from 2017-2021 (Passers)

Subject Area	June 2017	Dec. 2017	June 2018	Dec. 2018	June 2019	Dec. 2019	June 2020	Dec. 2020	June 2021	Dec. 2021	Gen. Ave.	Rank
<i>Criminal Law and Jurisprudence(CLJ)</i>	77.5	77.31	75.4	77.52	77.30	77.56	0	0	0	78.26	77.26	5
<i>Law Enforcement Administration(LEA)</i>	76.25	80.87	83	78.52	80.92	79.53	0	0	0	81.66	80.10	1
<i>Criminalistics(C)</i>	76	75.87	78.6	76.76	77.07	79.86	0	0	0	77.93	77.44	4
<i>Crime Detection and Investigation(CD&I)</i>	73.75	80.75	81.6	80.66	79.15	84.03	0	0	0	80.46	80.05	2
<i>Criminal Sociology, Ethics and Human Relation(CS,EHR)</i>	76.25	76.5	80	77.71	78	80.03	0	0	0	76.33	77.83	6
<i>Correctional Administration(CA)</i>	76.5	76.5	76.4	78.52	74.76	76.7	0	0	0	77.73	76.73	7
Weighted Mean	76.04	77.96	79.16	78.28	77.86	79.61	0	0	0	78.72	78.23	3

Source: Professional Regulation Commission (PRC)

Data revealed that the highest weighted average mean in all subject areas were in December 2019 with an average rating of 79.61 while the lowest subject were June 2017 with a weighted mean of 76.04. this implies that the performance of the examinees in the licensure examination is not consistent it needs more improvement specifically in major subjects to increase the performance rate of the examinees and institutional performance in the Licensure examination.

This is mentioned by Albite, R.P. (2020) that goal setting and knowing oneself; interest in reading and overlearning the material; being test-wise and understanding the nature of the LET, and attending a LET review program and committing to it. Five strong contributory attributes were also revealed such as: having metacognitive test-taking skills; strong faith in God; a good support system; a solid foundation in college; and active participation in a study group. The majority of them expressed their College’s contribution and influence to their success through competency-based instruction, quality faculty, and LET-type assessment. More intensive and extensive training and enhancement which focuses on the identified preparations and contributory attributes may be targeted to produce a common ground for effective teaching-learning practice for future graduates as stated by Dagdag, et al.,(2017)passing the Licensure Examination has been the ultimate focus of tertiary education

institutions in the Philippines. The performance of the examinees is influenced by low performances in academics and admission tests, and limited course audit units taken and admission test performance, however, do not predict performance in board examination. Rosales(2014) concluded that those who took the examination for the first time (first timers) performed better, and had a higher passing percentage and significantly higher average rating than repeaters in all the NLEs. The study reveals significant findings that correlate the performance of graduates of Philippine colleges of nursing in the 8 NLEs with selected variables and these findings may provide a better understanding of the issues and problems concerning the performance of examinees in the NLE.

Tan (2016) pointed out that the licensure examination review conducted by the school administration has a great impact on the passing performance of those who attended the review. Hence, he suggested the continuity in conducting the licensure examination review as an intervention program to improve the graduates’ performance. And there is also a need to unify the different review materials of lecturers in conjunction with the Table of Specifications as stipulated in the respective areas of disciplines and clusters.

Chua (2018) This study showed that they spend more than 8 hours in the evening preparing for the examination. They also understood the concept first before proceeding with practical application. The candidates also used self-assessment to evaluate themselves for the examination.

Table 4 depicts the data on the Weighted Average mean of the examinees per subject area in the licensure examination for criminologists of the Non-Passers from 2017 –

2021. interpreted from highest to lowest rank. The following data shows that rank 1, Law Enforcement Administration were 64.36 mean average, rank 2, Crime Detection and Investigation with 60.50, rank 3, Criminalistics 60.27, rank 4, is the general weighted average mean of 59.74, rank 5, criminal law and jurisprudence, 58.31 and the lowest were rank 6, criminal Sociology, Ethics, and Human Behavior, 57.07, rank 7 Correctional Administration with 57.93 average mean.

Table 4: General Weighted Average (GWA) of the Examinees per Subject Area in the Licensure Examinations for Criminologist Every Examination from 2017-2021 (Non-Passers)

Subject Area	June 2017	Dec. 2017	June 2018	Dec. 2018	June 2019	Dec. 2019	June 2020	Dec. 2020	June 2021	Dec. 2021	Gen. Ave.	Rank
<i>Criminal Law and Jurisprudence (CLJ)</i>	60.90	56.38	58.92	58.25	56.2	60.62	0	0	0	56.95	58.31	5
<i>Law Enforcement Administration (LEA)</i>	60.70	62.02	60.96	64.41	68.4	64.58	0	0	0	69.45	64.36	1
<i>Criminalistics (C)</i>	60.67	58.16	55.84	58.01	62.32	65.06	0	0	0	61.85	60.27	3
<i>Crime Detection and Investigation (CD&I)</i>	55.35	59.97	55.38	58.10	62.72	67.22	0	0	0	64.82	60.50	2
<i>Criminal Sociology, Ethics and Human Relation (CS, EHR)</i>	54.06	52.71	53.84	56.19	63.88	60.54	0	0	0	58.32	57.07	6
<i>Correctional Administration (CA)</i>	60.09	54.04	55.15	60.12	57.92	58.52	0	0	0	59.7	57.93	7
Weighted Mean	58.62	57.21	56.68	59.18	61.90	62.75	0	0	0	61.84	59.74	4

Source: Professional Regulation Commission (PRC)

Interestingly the data are shown in the Licensure Examination Performance of the examinees based on the ranking of the subject areas they have consonant; the Law enforcement is in the rank 1 while in the lowest rank were the Correctional Administration Subject. This trend implies that the strength of the faculty in the Criminology Department of Solis Institute of Technology is in Law Enforcement Administration while the weakness were in Correctional Administration. Therefore the School Administration should encourage and support their faculty in upgrading their knowledge and continues training in seminars for those under the weak subject areas and should hire competent faculty with specialized in correctional administration.

The result of the data interpreted was supported by the study of Teredano, Cruz, and Peralta (2019), the respondents did well in five performance areas in the CLE except in Criminalistics. The results also showed that five of the six performance areas evaluated had the interpretation of Good except for Correctional Administration (CA). No significant correlation was found between academic performance and CLE rating which means that the good academic performance of the students in college in the three areas such as Sociology of Crime and Ethics (CRIMSOC), Law enforcement Administration (LEA), and CA do not necessarily assure them of the passing of the CLE.

In addition, the college of Criminology should update and realign the curriculum of the Criminology program that

can be adopted in students learning outcomes this is supported by Laguador and Dizon (2013) cited that an outcome-based curriculum must be adopted periodically to monitor the academic performance and behavior as well as the result of the study habits of the students. The teachers must consistently provide monitor the academic performance and behavior of students to provide thorough guidance for those who are low achievers. The result of this study is consistent with that of Howell, Kurns, and Antil (2013) explicating that the curriculum being offered in higher education programs is intended to prepare students to achieve minimum competencies related to a specific vocation or profession.

Another study supported this statement, Casama, C. & Ventayan, O. (2020) Institutions aim to improve the licensure examination result for teacher education. It has been a practice in ensuring quality education to its client through continuously improving its various teacher education programs, engaging learners in the real teaching-learning situation. Academic predictors were identified as the result of the study, and it is recommended that state universities and colleges, and other private institutions should adopt several methods to achieve a high passing percentage.

Pregoner, JD.M. (2020) in his study disentangle the stories of unsuccessful LET examinees, their responses to failure, and their perspectives on the factors that contributed to their failure. Factors related to the physical environment,

psychological well-being, and preparedness influenced the performance of the examinees. Contributory factors to failure provided several implications for teacher education practice. The economic status of the examinees, library facilities, instructional materials, educational achievement of the instructors/professors, length of service, specialization, training, and seminars attended are cited by Baang M.A., (2013). Educators have a responsibility to identify, inform, and intervene with students who are at high risk of failing the exam, and this responsibility could be executed capably. The role should be extended beyond graduation. The responsibility to help graduates transition from failure to licensure is the final step of successful undergraduate teacher education.

Hence, Antiojo (2017) stated that the institutions' passing percentage in terms of the number of passers, on the average, is above the LET National Passing Percentage for both the secondary and elementary education graduates are in compliant with the minimum requirements of the Commission on Higher mandates Possible interventions were suggested to strengthen instructions and enhance LET Performance. It is likewise recommended to study the predictors of LET Performance in future research.

C. Correlation Between the Academic Performance and Licensure Examination Result of the Examinees in the Licensure Examination for Criminologists from 2017 – 2021

Table 5 revealed the correlation between the academic Performance and the Licensure Examination result of the Examinees in the Licensure Examination for Criminologists from 2017 – 2021. The Correlation of the two variables were determined by Pearson Correlation Coefficient. This test were used to determine the significant relationship between the General Weighted Mean of student's academic performance and the General Weighted mean of the licensure examination per subject areas of the examinees, passers and non-passers, were in 0.05 level of significance. The result shows that for the passers examinees the computed value of -0.1062 is negatively had a weak correlation and no significant relationship between academic performance and licensure examination result. Similar presented in the non-passer, the computed value of 0.6776 was moderately positively correlated and had no significant relationship between the two computed variables.

Table 5: Correlation Between the Academic Performance and Licensure Examination Result of the Examinees in the Licensure Examination for Criminologists from 2017 - 2021

	Level of Significance	P-Value	r.05	Decision	Conclusion
Passers	.05	.802367	-0.1062	Negative/Weak Correlated	Not Significant
	.05	.064826	0.6776	Moderately Positive Correlate	Not Significant
Non - Passers	.05				

It implies that even the there is a negative weak correlation of the academic performance in the licensure examination, the student's school performance is a good indicator of passing the board examination.it is reflected that the strict implementation of the retention policy, revision of the curriculum that can adapt to the learning needs of the students to be able to improve and achieved a higher chance of passing the exam and increase institutional performance percentage. As cited by Faltado, et. Al.,(2014) stated that the results of the study divulged that type of school is not a factor in passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers. Admission and retention policy, curriculum and instruction, and faculty competence are significantly correlated with the teacher education program performance in the licensure examination.

According to Garcia, G. C. (2013), the correlation coefficient between the examinee's academic performance and licensure examination rating is very high in the Field of Specialization subjects, weak positive correlation in the Professional Education subjects. However, the correlation in examinees' academic and Licensure Examination for Teachers rating, in general, is moderately significant. The

academic performance (grade average) of examinees gives no assurance (not a determinant) of passing the PRC (LET) examination.

Based on the study of Badua (2020), Results revealed that the respondents are moderately good in their academic performance and obtained a passing average in the criminology licensure examination. This implies that the licensure performance needs improvement to obtain a higher institutional passing over the national passing and is wanting for improvement. The takers had treated the board examination as average. Further, the correlation between the Academic Performance and Licensure Performance rating is negatively high. Hence, their rating is dependent on the performance of the students. Student study habits, poor faculty instruction, poor review class management, financial and health problems were encountered by the respondents in school, review, and board examination.

V. CONCLUSION

The academic performance of the examinees who passed the licensure examination has very satisfactory verbal interpretation based on the scheduled examination. All their weighted average mean was 85 and above. While those who unsuccessfully passed the exam have only 81 – 84.25 grade bracket which means they were consonantly in satisfactory verbal interpretation. The performance in the licensure examination for Criminologists of the examinees of Solis Institute of Technology (passers and Non – Passers) showed that they have consonants; they have both high weighted averages mean in subject areas of Law Enforcement Administration and Lowest average mean in the subject area of Correctional Administration. There is a negative weak correlation between the academic performance concerning licensure examination, the academic performance of the graduates who passed the licensure examination, and those who failed the examination, their correlations were moderately positively correlated to each other.

RECOMMENDATION

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendation were formulated; It is therefore recommended that the College of Criminology should strengthen their retention and admission policies, program curriculum offers, and delivery to improve the student outcome learning during their four years of studies. Administrators should craft a comprehensive professional development plan to support teachers in pursuing post-graduate studies and other academic endeavors that could equip them to become more effective teacher educators. The faculty member should participate in training and seminars related to the 6 subject areas that are part of the curriculum program that would help to fully equipped with knowledge, skills, and values that could be a vital factor in producing competitive highly competitive criminology professionals in the industry, the school administration played a vital role as well. The school administration and college of criminology should re-evaluate the curriculum program and realigned it that adopt to students learning outcomes, formulation of course syllabi based on the policy and standard guidelines for criminology education, and table of specifications of the professional regulation commission. Implement a further study evaluating the instruction and assessment strategies of faculty of teaching the major subjects in criminology program to be a basis in cascading the intervention program for the improvement of the student's performance in 6 major subject areas.

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AUTHORS' INFORMATION FORM**ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF CRIMINOLOGY GRADUATES AND ITS IMPACT ON THE LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR CRIMINOLOGIST**

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